

Please! Mind the (gender) Gap: A Comparative Analysis of Fare-Free Public Transport Policies for Women in Seven Indian States¹

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Abstract

This study provides the first comparative analysis of fare-free public transport (FFPT) policies for women across seven Indian states. The research compares the urban transport policy reforms of Delhi, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Kerala, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, and Telangana. All seven reforms share a common objective: providing *fare-free travel* and *enhanced safety* to women in state public buses. These policies aim to address key barriers to women's urban mobility, particularly high transport costs and safety concerns, which often limit their social and economic participation. Using secondary administrative data and published empirical evidence, the research examines the policies to assess the effects on women in India. The preliminary findings indicate a consistent pattern of increased ridership, improved affordability, and measurable household savings, with positive implications for women's employment access and social inclusion across all seven states. However, the magnitude of these impacts varies across states due to differences in infrastructure capacity, fiscal sustainability, and policy design. The analysis identifies common benefits and recurring challenges, including overcrowding, fiscal pressure, and the exclusion of certain vulnerable groups. The study highlights fare-free public transport as a promising gender-responsive policy tool and outlines conditions under which such schemes are most likely to advance women's empowerment.

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1. Introduction

Urban transport costs and safety concerns are widely recognized as major barriers to women's mobility in the Global South, limiting their access to education, employment, healthcare, and social participation. In India, these concerns are particularly pronounced among low-income and marginalized groups, who often rely on public transport for daily mobility. Evidence across global and Indian contexts consistently shows that women often modify, restrict, or avoid travel when public transport is unaffordable or perceived as unsafe. Such travel behavior results in reduced economic participation and diminished autonomy.

To address these concerns, the state of Delhi implemented the Pink Pass policy in 2019, granting fare-free travel to all women in public buses. The policy was designed to improve both affordability and safety, with the broader objective of enhancing women's social and economic empowerment. By 2025, six additional Indian states—Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Kerala, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, and Telangana—adopted similar schemes. Such schemes, with common agendas for women's empowerment, represent a significant shift toward gender-responsive urban mobility in India. Although these seven policies share a common objective of providing fare-free, safer urban transport, their designs, eligibility rules, operational capacities, and implementation strategies vary substantially.

There is limited comparative evidence on whether these policies generate consistent outcomes across different socio-economic and institutional contexts. Such variation creates a unique opportunity to analyze whether similar interventions generate consistent empowerment outcomes across diverse socio-economic and institutional contexts. The lack of systematic comparison creates an important gap in understanding the overall effectiveness and scalability of fare-free public transport as a policy tool for women's empowerment. This study addresses this gap by systematically analyzing seven state-level fare-free public transport schemes for women. This research aims to (i) *conduct a comparative analysis of the 7 sister policies³, implemented across seven respective states in India*, and (ii) *assess whether these policies have contributed to women's social and economic empowerment*.

Using secondary literature and administrative data, the study identifies key patterns in policy outcomes, including improvements in affordability, household savings, mobility, and access

³ In this research, 7 sister policies mean 7 policies of fare-free urban transport in 7 Indian states of Delhi, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Kerala, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, and Telangana

to employment. At the same time, it highlights variations across states in terms of implementation, operational capacity, and policy effectiveness. This study contributes to the literature in three important ways. First, it provides one of the first systematic comparative analyses of fare-free public transport policies across seven Indian states using a unified analytical framework. Second, it identifies both common patterns and state-level variations in policy outcomes, thereby improving understanding of the conditions under which such policies are most effective. Third, it contributes to broader policy debates on gender-sensitive urban transport by assessing the potential of fare-free mobility interventions to advance women's empowerment in developing country contexts.

This working paper is organized into eight sections. Section 2 presents the literature review, followed by Section 3, which offers a critical assessment of existing research. Section 4 outlines the hypotheses and research questions. Section 5 describes the data and methodological approach, while Section 6 provides a description of reforms across seven states. Section 7 discusses policy implications and concludes in Section 8.

2. Related literature

Despite the growing body of literature on urban transport affordability and safety, several important gaps remain. Existing research is largely fragmented and geographically limited, with most studies focusing on single cities or individual states.

2.1 Global evidence on the relationship between fare-free urban transport and gender mobility

Globally, fare-free public transport (FFPT) has gained traction as a tool to improve accessibility and mobility of dependent groups. Studies from Tallinn (Estonia) and Luxembourg demonstrate increased ridership and enhanced accessibility after FFPT implementation, especially among low-income, young, and transit-dependent users (Cats et al., 2017; Pires, 2024). Research also suggests that FFPT can advance gender equality: Maciejewska (2024) argues that fare-free schemes function as gender-sensitive policies by removing systemic cost barriers that disproportionately affect women. The author suggests that fare-free transport can function as a gender-sensitive policy by reducing financial barriers and enhancing women's mobility and

autonomy. Transport affordability is widely recognized as a key determinant of mobility in both developed and developing contexts. Studies often define urban transport affordability as the ability to meet mobility needs without imposing a disproportionate financial burden (Carruthers et al., 2005; Dewita et al., 2020; Litman, 2021). For women, affordability plays a particularly critical role, as it directly influences their empowerment (Sahay, 1998; Chattopadhyay, 2005). Empirical research across countries shows that high transport costs are disproportionately to mobility constraints and limit women's socio-economic participation (Tracey-White, 2005; Dominguez Gonzalez et al., 2020; Priye & Manoj, 2020). Transport costs impose gendered burdens, with women facing higher relative expenses due to trip chaining and lower incomes. Litman (2021b) advocates smart mobilities for equity, while Fan and Huang (2011) develop affordability indices sensitive to context. In low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), Carruthers et al. (2005) and Dewita et al. (2020) document exclusionary effects.

Beyond affordability, global evidence overwhelmingly shows that women face disproportionate safety-related constraints in public transport environments. Studies from the U.S., U.K., Chile, Ecuador, Pakistan, South Africa, and Ethiopia reveal persistent experiences of sexual harassment, fear of victimization, and avoidance of routes, modes, or travel times (Carter, 2005a; Hsu, 2011; Allen & Vanderschuren, 2016a; Korn, 2018; King et al., 2023). Women's strategies often involve modifying travel behaviors, reducing mobility, or shifting to more expensive modes of transportation — creating a gendered mobility gap. Studies from multiple countries document the widespread prevalence of harassment and violence against women in public transport systems (Carter, 2005b; Allen & Vanderschuren, 2016b; Jennings et al., 2022). These safety concerns significantly alter travel behaviour, leading women to avoid certain routes, travel times, or modes of transport, often at additional financial cost. Large-scale surveys further confirm that a majority of women globally modify their mobility patterns due to fear of harassment (Hollaback & Cornell University, 2016). Overall, the global literature establishes that affordability and safety are two critical and interrelated determinants of gendered mobility, with direct implications for socio-economic empowerment. Therefore, mobility is a dual problem of affordability and safety, in which both dimensions may jointly influence travel behaviour, autonomy, and women's socioeconomic participation.

2.2 Relationship between urban transport and women's mobility in India

In the Indian context, the barriers to women's urban transport mobility are well documented. It highlights the strong interlinkages between transport access, gender, and economic participation. High transport costs and limited availability of affordable public mobility continue to restrict women's ability to access education, employment, and essential services (Lei et al., 2019; Dominguez Gonzalez et al., 2020b). Empirical evidence further demonstrates that urban transport positively affects women's labor market outcomes. Using data from the Indian Human Development Survey, Lei et al. (2019b) find that enhanced transport connectivity increases women's participation in non-farm employment. Similarly, Dasgupta and Datta (2023a) provide robust evidence that fare reductions under Delhi's Pink Pass policy led to measurable increases in women's labor force participation and in the time spent in paid work.

In addition to affordability constraints, safety concerns represent a critical barrier to women's mobility across Indian cities. In Western countries, travel to India is often considered unsafe for women. A travel advisory issued by a United Kingdom-based portal classified travel to India as particularly unsafe for women (FCDO, 2024). Safety concerns in Indian urban transport are equally pervasive across cities such as Delhi, Chennai, Lucknow, Mumbai, Bangalore, Indore, Bhopal, and Ahmedabad. Reports consistently show high rates of verbal and physical harassment, stalking, unwanted touching, and fear-based travel modifications (Jagori & UN Women, 2011; Mitra-Sarkar & Partheeban, 2011; Tripathi et al., 2017; Verma et al., 2020). These concerns significantly influence women's travel behaviour, often leading them to choose safer but more expensive travel options or avoid travel altogether (Borker, 2021; Bhattacharya & Kopf, 2017). Hence, the literature suggests that both affordability and safety pose structural challenges with direct implications for women's social and economic participation in urban India.

2.3. Overview of FFPT schemes in 7 Indian states

Delhi was the first state to introduce a women-exclusive fare-free bus scheme through the *Pink Pass* policy in 2019. The reform sought to advance women's empowerment by addressing two core mobility constraints: affordability of urban transport and safety, through measures such as bus marshals, surveillance, and gender-sensitive operations.

Following Delhi's initiative, six additional states—Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Kerala, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, and Telangana—implemented similar policy interventions of fare-free urban transport to women. These policy replications indicate a broader shift toward recognizing transport affordability as a strategic instrument for advancing gender equity in urban mobility. In Figure 1, I illustrate *seven* Indian states that implemented fare-free or women-only subsidized public transport.

Figure 1. Map of India with 7 sister policy states

Source: Author

Note: (i) The map of India showing seven states with fare-free /subsidized public transport for women; (ii) Such seven states are highlighted in pink color; (iii) The abbreviations indicate as DL-Delhi, PB-Punjab, TN-Tamil Nadu, KL-Kerala, HP-Himachal Pradesh, KA-Karnataka, and TL-Telangana; (iv) The states in the orange color have no relevance in this study and indicate a disputed territory of India.

Table 1 summarizes the key features of these policies, including eligibility, scope, and implementation timelines.

Table 1. Key features of 7 sister policies

State	Scheme name	Implementation date	Target group	Scope
Delhi	Pink Pass Policy	29 th October 2019	All women	Fare-free travel in all Delhi public buses
Punjab	No scheme name provided	1 st April 2021	All women	Fare-free travel on non-air-conditioned state buses
Tamil Nadu	Zero-Ticket Bus Travel (ZTBT)	7 th May 2021	Women, transgender individuals, and persons with disabilities	Free travel up to 30 km/day on non-AC state buses
Kerala	Samudra	29 th August 2021	Women fish vendors, low-income students	Free buses between 5 pm and 10 pm; extended to students in Nov 2023
Himachal Pradesh	Naari ko Naman	30 th June 2022	All women	50% fare discount; female drivers hired under Ride with Pride
Karnataka	Shakti	11 th June 2023	All women	Free travel on non-air-conditioned buses
Telangana	Maha Laxmi	9 th December 2023	All women	Free travel on state buses

Source: Author

Note: (i) Pink Pass policy was the first scheme in India to implement fare-free urban transport for women; (ii) Column indicators represent key dimensions of policy outcomes as defined by the author.

While these studies provide valuable insights into individual policy outcomes, they lack a comprehensive comparative understanding of how similar policies perform across different states with varying socio-economic and institutional contexts. Sections 2.3.1 to 2.3.7 comprehensively discuss the benefits and limitations of the 7 sister policies based on administrative data and limited empirical evidence.

2.3.1 Delhi: Implementation of Pink Pass policy on 29th October 2019

Government data indicate an increase in women's bus ridership from 33% pre-implementation to 40% in the intervention period (Observatory of Public Sector Innovation, 2023). The number of Pink Pass users reached over 1 billion⁴ from the policy implementation until January 2023 (Raj, 2023). Before the pandemic lockdown, the state recorded over 1.6 billion Pink Pass users, increasing from 2019 to 2020 to 710 million, with a 25% growth during the 2020-2021 pandemic lockdown. The number of pink pass users increased to 1.25 billion, with 28% growth during the 2021-22 post-pandemic period and 33% growth until February 2023 (Jain, 2023). The state's data recorded over 4 million daily pink pass users and over 1,000 million pink passes between October 2019 and January 2023 (Raj, 2023b). Women's mobility on Delhi public buses increased by 10% after treatment (Chen et al., 2024). In addition to mobility gains, the policy generated measurable economic benefits. Administrative data indicate an increase in monthly household savings, ranging from ₹260 (€2.79) to ₹400 (€4.29) (Goswami, 2021). Furthermore, the policy contributed to improved labor market outcomes, with evidence showing a 24 percentage point increase in women's labor force participation at the extensive margin and an increase of approximately 150 minutes in work duration at the intensive margin (Dasgupta & Datta, 2023b).

Despite these positive outcomes, the policy also faces several limitations and challenges. One major concern relates to fiscal sustainability. The Delhi government reimburses bus operators approximately ₹10 (€0.11) per Pink Pass trip, with projected annual expenditures reaching ₹3,000 million (€33.4 million) (Mathur, 2019). Such a limitation raises questions regarding the long-term financial viability of the scheme. Although the state expanded the bus fleet size before the policy implementation, issues such as overcrowding, long wait times, and buses bypassing stops with high female demand persist (Behal, 2023). These constraints may limit the policy's effectiveness in fully addressing mobility barriers. Therefore, concerns have been raised about the policy's inclusivity. Critics argue that the scheme disproportionately benefits women while overlooking other vulnerable groups, such as individuals with disabilities and economically disadvantaged populations. Evidence suggests that a significant proportion of disabled women continue to face infrastructural barriers in accessing public transport (Kar et al., 2020).

⁴ Changed from Indian Rs100 crore.

2.3.2 Punjab state's fare-free public buses for women: Implemented on 1st April 2021

Punjab introduced its fare-free public bus scheme for women on 1 April 2021, enabling women to travel without charge on state-owned, non-air-conditioned buses by presenting a valid state identification card. The reform aimed to increase women's economic participation by offering affordable transportation (Express News Service, 2021).

The policy generated rapid and substantial ridership growth. From April 2021 until November 2022, women ridership doubled from 61.18 lakh (over 6 million) to 1.12 crore (over 11 million). In 2022-23, 14.29 crore (approx. 143 million) rides were recorded, and in 2023-24, nearly 14.90 crore (149 million) women's rides were recorded. Between 1 April and 15 July 2024, an additional 32 million trips were recorded (Hindustan Times, 2022; Singh, 2025; Vasdev, 2025). These trends indicate a sustained increase in women's reliance on public bus transport following the policy intervention. Beyond increased ridership, the policy is associated with improvements in women's access to education, employment, and healthcare services. Official sources suggest that the scheme has enhanced women's independence, dignity, and overall mobility (Punjab Newline Bureau, 2024).

The policy, however, faces several limitations and challenges. A key concern relates to fiscal sustainability. The annual policy budget cost is approximately Rs800 crore (€8 billion), compared with the planned cost of Rs450 crore (€4.5 billion) in 2023–24. Until March 2025, the Punjab state owed over Rs 700 crore (€7 billion) to the Punjab Road Transport Corporation (PRTC) and other agencies for subsidising fare-free buses for women (Singh, 2025). The policy has also generated unintended negative spillovers on private transport operators. Evidence suggests that women's ridership in private buses declined by up to 40% following the policy's implementation, adversely affecting the livelihoods of approximately 125,000 workers associated with the Punjab Motor Union (Hindustan Times, 2024). Operational inefficiencies further undermine the scheme's effectiveness. Since eligibility is restricted to women residents of Punjab, bus conductors require manual identification verification, which delays boarding. Although a smart card system has been proposed to streamline this process, it remains under consideration (Tribune News Service, 2025). Additionally, reports indicate persistent issues such as buses bypassing stops with high female demand, which may limit accessibility despite increased ridership (Behal, 2023b).

2.3.3 State of Tamil Nadu: Implementation of Zero Ticket Bus Travel Policy (ZBTP) for women on 7th May 2021

Tamil Nadu introduced the Zero-Ticket Bus Travel Policy (ZTBT) on 7 May 2021, providing fare-free travel in non-air-conditioned buses operated by the Tamil Nadu State Transport Corporation (TNSTC). The scheme extends benefits to women, transgender persons, and individuals with disabilities (at a rate of 40% or more), to enhance social well-being and increase labour market participation (Durai, 2021). The policy has led to significant improvements in women's urban mobility and access to socio-economic opportunities. Survey data indicate that 76.7% of women used ZTBT for social trips, while 59.3% used it for work-related commuting (Premkumar et al., 2024).

Findings from Coimbatore and Sivagangai districts reveal that more than 90% of ZTBT beneficiaries were working women, with 69.3% employed in the informal sector, demonstrating the scheme's role in expanding employment access for economically vulnerable groups (Manikandan et al., 2024). The scheme has also generated notable financial benefits. A survey report by the Tamil Nadu Planning Commission (2022) shows that 61.3% of women saved between Rs250 and Rs500 (€250 to €5) while 35% saved up to Rs1500 (€15) each month from fare-free rides. The average monthly savings range from Rs756 to Rs1012 (€8 to €10) across the Chennai, Madurai, Nagapattinam, and Tirupur districts (Kandavel, 2023). The state report further showed that the scheme helped 79.3% of women save money, and 14% found it a significant source of financial support. Women reportedly used the savings to repay loans, invest in business or PPF savings, and pay daily household expenses. The policy saved Rs 13000 (€130) in bus costs per student annually. The survey report's average respondent called for better quality and broader benefits. A comparative evaluation report in the Sivagangai district showed that more than 90% working women improved access to jobs and further studies. 59.3% used it for work, followed by education and essential errands. The policy enabled rural girls to access college travel, which had previously been unaffordable.

Despite these positive outcomes, the scheme faces several challenges. Reports show rude or dismissive conductors discouraged women from using fare-free public transport. Such behavior often involved mocking women for not paying the fares (Premkumar et al., 2024b). Such behavior perceives the gender-based resentment among male staff. These constraints are further compounded by delays, poor scheduling, and buses skipping stops during peak hours, all of

which reduce service reliability. Women expressed positive attitudes towards the policy but noted overcrowding, delays, and safety concerns. 30.7% of women among bus riders reported overcrowding. In comparison, 22.7% noted a lack of frequent buses, especially in the early morning and late night. Women with disabilities had limited access due to inadequate bus infrastructure, such as a lack of ramps or a suitable bus design. Reports show that buses often have poor time management and skip during peak hours due to crowding (Premkumar et al., 2024d). As a result, some women continue to rely on private transport options despite the availability of fare-free services.

2.3.4 Kerala: Implementation of Samudra bus service on 29th August 2021

Kerala introduced the *Samudra [Sea in English] Bus Service* on August 29, 2021. The service provides three fare-free buses between 5 am and 10 pm exclusively to women fish vendors from coastal areas to the city. The scheme aims to empower women from the fisheries sector, promote their economic well-being, and alleviate the monthly financial burden of Rs400-500 (€4.45 to €5.55). The state extended the scheme benefits for low-income family students in November 2023 (TNN, 2021a; Pegu, 2025).

In contrast, empirical evidence on the scheme's outcomes remains limited. As of June 2025, no official data on ridership, income improvements, or broader socio-economic impacts have been publicly reported (Kerala State Planning Board, 2023). The absence of impact evaluations and cost-benefit analyses restricts a comprehensive assessment of the policy's effectiveness. The scheme also faces several operational and structural limitations. A key constraint is its limited operational scale, with only three buses deployed under the service. This restricts its capacity to adequately meet the mobility needs of the target population, particularly given the dispersed nature of coastal communities (TNN, 2021b). As of the 2025-26 Gender Budget, no impact evaluations, ridership data, or cost-benefit reports are publicly available (Kerala State Planning Board, 2023b, Chapter 8). Outcome measures like increased income or improved business mobility are missing. Furthermore, the scheme's narrow targeting raises concerns regarding inclusivity. While it primarily benefits coastal fisherwomen—and, more recently, low-income students—it excludes other vulnerable groups such as non-coastal informal women workers and urban low-income vendors. This selective coverage suggests an uneven distribution of public transport benefits across socio-economic groups (TNN, 2021c).

2.3.5 Himachal Pradesh: Implementation of Naari ko Naman scheme on 30th June 2022

Himachal Pradesh introduced the Naari ko Naman (Salute to Women) scheme on 30 June 2022, offering a 50% fare discount on public bus travel for women with monthly household incomes below Rs 10,000 (100€). The initiative also included recruiting 25 female drivers under the state's *Ride with Pride* government taxi program, reflecting an effort to expand women's participation in the transport workforce (Arora, 2022; Sarkari Yojana Team, 2022). The scheme has yielded limited positive outcomes and faces several structural challenges. Transport department data indicate that overall bus ridership declined by approximately 12%, from 150,000 to 132,000 daily commuters within the first six months of implementation (Himachal Pradesh Transport Department, 2023). While the policy was intended to encourage women's mobility, the observed decline suggests possible unintended behavioural or demand-side effects. The decline suggests discouragement of other user groups, creating unintended distributional consequences.

National Sample Survey Office (NSSO) data reveal that the average monthly income for low-income households, including people dependent on public transport for work, is below ₹10,000. Broader socioeconomic evidence indicates that many low-income households earning below ₹10,000 per month rely heavily on public transport for work (Pant, 2019). However, because the scheme restricts benefits exclusively to women, it unintentionally excludes other marginalized groups, including the elderly, persons with disabilities, and economically disadvantaged men. This exclusion raises concerns about unequal access, increased transport-related disparities, and limited fairness in redistribution (Department of Economic Affairs, 2021).

2.3.6 Karnataka: Implementation of Shakti Scheme on 11th June 2023

Karnataka introduced the Shakti Scheme on 11 June 2023, providing fare-free travel to women on state-owned, non-air-conditioned buses (Kumar, 2023). The policy aims to enhance women's mobility, reduce financial burdens, and support greater participation in economic and social activities. In the first month, the women's ridership accounted for over 167 million trips, and by November 2023, cumulative ridership exceeded 1 billion journeys. Survey findings indicate that

approximately 5.5 million women use Shakti buses daily, with around 7% reporting that they began using public buses *only after* the scheme's introduction (Chakravarthy & Seth, 2024). Although the data does not reveal the pre-reform comparative figures, the fare exemption also yielded substantial financial benefits. Women collectively saved over ₹24 billion (€0.24 billion) on fare-free rides. The average monthly household savings of women in the city of Bengaluru is Rs 1,326 (€13) and Rs 1,015 (€10) in Haveri. These savings were frequently reallocated toward food, education, health, and other essential household expenditures. Beyond financial relief, the scheme enhanced women's economic and social opportunities. Over 60% of women reported improved access to work and a willingness to travel longer distances for economic activities. Additionally, 84% of women identified public buses as their preferred mode of commuting, while 33% used the scheme for leisure, community engagement, family visits, or healthcare needs (Chakravarthy & Seth, 2024b).

Despite these positive outcomes, the Shakti Scheme faces considerable operational pressures. Survey data show that 77% of respondents—men and women—experienced overcrowded buses after implementation, with average waiting times increasing by more than 15 minutes in cities such as Bengaluru, Haveri, and Yadgir (Chakravarthy & Seth, 2024c). Service quality and accessibility issues also persist in certain regions. In districts such as Udipi and Chamarajanagar, limited bus frequency and connectivity have led a significant proportion of women to rely on private transport options. Evidence suggests that over 72% of women in these areas prefer private buses due to better availability, punctuality, and seating comfort, with nearly 47% citing shorter waiting times as a key factor. Additionally, instances of perceived disrespectful behaviour by fellow passengers and transport staff have been reported, although qualitative evidence suggests that their prevalence remains relatively limited (Chakravarthy & Seth, 2024c).

2.3.7 Telangana: Implementation of the Maha Laxmi policy on 9th December 2023

Telangana introduced the Maha Laxmi (meaning *Super Wealth*) scheme on 9 December 2023, offering fare-free bus travel for women and transgender individuals on non-luxury state buses (Gautam, 2023). Eligibility is limited to women and transgender residents aged 18–55 years, with annual household incomes under Rs 3 lakh (€2,970) belonging to the Scheduled Castes, the Scheduled Tribes, or the Other Backwards Castes. Beneficiaries may travel free on interstate

Express and Palle Velugu buses up to the state border, with the state reimbursing TSRTC for the cost of subsidized rides (Telangana Nava-Nirmanana Sena, 2023).

The policy has resulted in a substantial increase in public transport usage. Empirical evidence indicates that overall ridership increased by approximately 53% following implementation (Yasa, 2024). Daily female ridership rose from 1.4 million to 3 million, while monthly ridership increased from 2.7 million in December 2023 to 3.15 million in March 2024 (Telangana Today, 2024). The scheme has generated significant financial benefits for households. Prior to implementation, women reportedly spent approximately Rs1,500 (€15) per month on bus travel. Following the policy, cumulative savings exceeded ₹1,177 crore (€0.12 billion) within four months and reached over ₹2,840 crore (€28 billion) by September 2024 (Reddy, 2024; The Hans India, 2024). These savings have contributed to improved household welfare and increased financial flexibility. In addition to monetary relief, beneficiaries reported greater mobility, improved access to employment, education, and healthcare services, suggesting emerging socio-economic empowerment effects (Yasa, 2024b; Telangana Today, 2024b). The surge in demand increased occupancy rates—often above 100%—prompting TSRTC to expand its fleet by procuring 1,050 new diesel buses and 550 electric buses for intercity routes.

Despite considerable benefits, the Maha Laxmi scheme presents significant operational and social challenges. A comparative perceptual study found issues of overcrowding, increased workloads for bus staff, and disruption for male passengers following implementation. Reports also documented instances where male passengers and staff displayed contempt or disdain toward fare-free female riders, leading some women to feel stigmatized as *freeloaders*. Several structural barriers remain unaddressed. The scheme does not include investments in bus infrastructure or safety measures, despite widespread concerns regarding poor accessibility, uncomfortable or poorly maintained buses, and heightened risk of harassment in overcrowded vehicles (Kumar & Sekhar, 2024). Issues such as inadequate fleet size, poor maintenance, limited accessibility, and insufficient first- and last-mile connectivity persist. The scheme also raises concerns regarding inclusivity and accessibility. Eligibility restrictions based on income, age, and residence, along with the requirement to present identity documentation, may exclude certain vulnerable groups. Furthermore, the policy has generated adverse spillover effects on private transport operators, including taxi and auto-rickshaw drivers, due to reduced demand.

3. Critical literature review

Despite extensive studies on the affordability and safety of urban transport for women, the literature identifies five critical limitations. Such gaps are justified as a contribution to this study.

3.1 Fragmentation and absence of comparative evidence

Existing research is largely fragmented and geographically limited, with most studies focusing on single cities or individual states. While there is substantial evidence from Delhi and selected Indian cities, there is a lack of systematic comparative analysis across multiple states implementing similar fare-free transport policies. For instance, existing studies on schemes such as Karnataka's Shakti or Tamil Nadu's zero-ticket travel are largely standalone analyses, lacking cross-state comparison or synthesis (Chakravarthy, 2023; Kumar, 2023). Delhi studies focus narrowly on the Pink Pass, while Kerala, Himachal Pradesh, and Punjab lack robust evaluations altogether. No study compares all seven Indian schemes despite their shared objectives, identical policy logic, and similar intended beneficiaries. This limits the ability to identify cross-state patterns in policy, success conditions, and policy effectiveness across diverse socio-economic and institutional contexts.

3.2 Methodological inconsistencies across studies

State-level literature relies on descriptive or perception-based analyses, with limited integration of structured comparative frameworks. Although studies document improvements in mobility, savings, and safety perceptions, they often lack a unified analytical framework for evaluating these outcomes across different policy settings. Tamil Nadu and Karnataka rely on small-sample surveys or perceptual studies. Kerala and Himachal Pradesh have almost no evaluative research. Telangana largely uses descriptive administrative reporting. As a result, the indicators and evaluation designs for existing findings remain context-specific and lack generalizability (Chakravarthy, 2023).

3.3 Absence of causal or configurational analysis

There is a lack of policy-oriented evaluation frameworks that link fare-free transport initiatives directly to measurable outcomes such as mobility patterns, labor participation, and socio-economic empowerment. Most studies stop documenting associations without systematically identifying patterns across policy environments. No existing study uses Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA) or any set-theoretical method to identify combinations of policy features that lead to empowerment outcomes. The current literature documents what happened in each state, but never asks: *which configurations of policy design and implementation conditions produce positive outcomes across states?* Thus, the causal pathways remain unexplored.

3.4. Safety and affordability are rarely studied together

Moreover, there is a disconnect between affordability-focused and safety-focused research. While one stream of literature emphasizes transport costs and economic access (Carruthers et al., 2005b; Litman, 2021b), another focuses on violence against women and safety concerns in public transport (Allen & Vanderschuren, 2016b; Jennings et al., 2022b). However, very few studies examine how these two dimensions interact simultaneously to influence women's mobility behaviour. For instance, Delhi is unique in integrating affordability with explicit safety measures (bus marshals, CCTV, GPS), but the literature does not analyze how these elements jointly affect empowerment. This represents a critical gap, particularly in the context of policies such as fare-free transport.

4. Hypotheses and research questions

This research shares two hypotheses.

H1: *The seven state-level women-exclusive fare-free public transport schemes exhibit similarities in their core policy objectives, design features, and implementation structures.*

H2: *The seven sister policies positively contribute to women's social and economic empowerment, though the impact varies across states due to differences in implementation quality, operational capacity, and supporting infrastructure.*

This research compares urban transport policies of all seven states by exploring *two* research questions:

1. *What are the key similarities and differences in the FFPT policies across seven states?*
2. *To what extent have the seven sister policies contributed to women's social and economic empowerment in their respective states?*

5. Data and methodology

This research combines qualitative policy analysis with quantitative and descriptive evidence drawn from administrative and secondary data sources. For each policy, the study examines three primary data sources. *First*, official policy documents, government notifications, and transport department reports are reviewed to identify the institutional features of each state-level scheme. *Second*, administrative indicators such as ridership trends, subsidy allocations, and operational statistics. *Third*, secondary evidence from existing empirical studies, survey reports, and institutional publications

Therefore, due to the heterogeneity of data quality and availability across the seven states, the analysis combines quantitative indicators (ridership, savings, coverage) and qualitative evidence (perceptions, operational constraints, policy evaluation reports). The objective is not to estimate causal effects but to generate policy-relevant insights within a coherent comparative framework. Such an approach is often appropriate due to the heterogeneity of data sources and the absence of harmonized datasets across all states.

With a small case universe ($N = 7$) and diverse policy structures, future extensions of this work may apply fuzzy set Qualitative Comparative Analysis (fsQCA) to identify configurations of factors such as universal eligibility, safety measures, ridership shifts, or subsidy models that jointly contribute to women's socioeconomic empowerment. Such an approach would complement the descriptive analysis presented here by revealing how different policy arrangements align with observed variations in women's mobility outcomes across states.

6. Comparative insights across states

A comparative analysis of the seven state-level fare-free public transport (FFPT) policies reveals several consistent patterns in benefits, as well as variations in implementation and

outcomes across states. Across all states, the primary benefits of FFPT policies are evident in increased ridership, improved financial savings, and enhanced access to economic and social opportunities for women. The policies have significantly reduced the cost burden of daily commuting, leading to measurable household savings and improved financial resilience. Evidence suggests that women frequently reallocate these savings toward essential expenditures, including food, education, and healthcare. Moreover, almost all 7-sister policies have contributed to improved labor market participation and mobility and greater social inclusion by increasing autonomy, reducing dependency on male household members, and increasing women's autonomy in travel decisions.

Despite these positive outcomes, the analysis also reveals several common challenges across states. A key limitation is overcrowding and operational inefficiencies, particularly in high-demand states such as Karnataka and Telangana. Fiscal unsustainability is another major concern for the long-term validity of such schemes. For instance, where the actual cost exceeds the anticipated cost in Punjab. Several policies exhibit limitations in inclusivity and accessibility. For instance, eligibility restrictions, identification, and inadequate technical infrastructure have excluded certain underprivileged or disabled groups. Behavioral and institutional challenges also persist. Reports of negative attitudes from transport staff and fellow passengers toward women beneficiaries highlight underlying gender biases that may undermine the intended objectives of these policies.

Overall, while FFPT policies demonstrate consistent positive impacts on affordability, mobility, and economic participation, their effectiveness varies across states due to differences in implementation capacity, infrastructure, and policy design. These findings highlight the importance of complementary measures to ensure the long-term success and scalability of such interventions.

7. Policy implications

The findings of this study offer several important policy implications for the design and implementation of fare-free urban transport systems for women. First, while fare-free policies effectively improve affordability and mobility, they must be complemented by investments in transport infrastructure. Increasing fleet size, improving service frequency, and enhancing first- and last-mile connectivity are essential to address overcrowding and ensure service reliability.

Second, fiscal sustainability should be a key consideration in policy design. Governments need to develop clear financing mechanisms, including budget allocation strategies and cost-sharing models, to ensure the long-term viability of such schemes without placing excessive pressure on state finances.

Third, policymakers should prioritize inclusivity and accessibility. Expanding eligibility criteria, simplifying documentation requirements, and improving infrastructure for women with disabilities can help ensure that the benefits of these policies reach a broader segment of the population.

Fourth, addressing safety concerns requires more than fare reductions. Investments in gender-sensitive transport measures such as surveillance systems, trained staff, and safe waiting areas are necessary to improve women's travel experiences and perceptions of safety.

Finally, behavioral and institutional factors must be addressed through awareness campaigns and staff training programs to reduce gender-based discrimination and improve the overall quality of service delivery.

8. Conclusion

This study provides the first systematic comparative analysis of seven state-level women-exclusive fare-free public transport schemes in India. The research highlights the policy's potential and limitations as a tool for enhancing women's socio-economic empowerment. The preliminary descriptive findings show that these interventions have collectively expanded women's access to safe and affordable urban mobility, enhanced financial independence through substantial monthly savings, and improved access to employment, education, and social services. By reducing transport-related financial barriers, FFPT schemes have improved household welfare and increased women's economic participation. States such as Delhi, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Punjab, and Telangana have achieved substantial mobility gains, supporting the hypothesis that fare-free transport can be an effective mechanism for women's social and economic empowerment.

Nevertheless, the policies also reveal important challenges. Narrow targeting (Kerala, Himachal Pradesh), insufficient fleet capacity (Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Telangana), and fiscal strain (Punjab, Delhi) constrain the extent to which fare-free mobility can deliver equitable and sustained benefits. The absence of integrated safety measures in several states further limits

potential empowerment outcomes and reduces the overall effectiveness of fare-free mobility initiatives.

While the study provides important insights, it is based primarily on secondary data and descriptive analysis. The preliminary findings suggest that while fare-free public transport is a promising gender-inclusive policy instrument, its success depends on broad eligibility, operational robustness, integration of safety measures, and financial sustainability. The findings in this research paper should be interpreted as indicative rather than causal. Future research should employ empirical methods to assess the long-term impact of FFPT policies on labor market outcomes, social inclusion, and gender equality. In conclusion, fare-free public transport policies represent a promising approach to enhancing women's empowerment in urban India. However, their success depends on effective implementation, adequate infrastructure, and the integration of complementary policy measures to ensure sustainable and inclusive outcomes.

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